

REVIEW OF CURRENT DATA ON GOLDEN HARE'S EAR (*BUPLEURUM AUREI* FISCH.) AND PROSPECTS FOR ITS USE IN PHARMACEUTICAL PRACTICE

Ashirov M.Z.
Toizhanov B.K.

S.D. Asfendiyarov Kazakh National Medical University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan
e-mail: ashirov.m@kaznmu.kz
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Relevance. Medicinal plants are a valuable source of biologically active substances (BAS). Among them, a promising object is golden hare's ear (*Bupleurum aurei* Fisch.), traditionally used in the treatment of liver and gastrointestinal diseases. Modern studies confirm its rich chemical composition and pharmacological potential.

Purpose of the study. To summarize data on the phytochemistry and pharmacological properties of *Bupleurum aurei*, as well as to assess the prospects for its use in pharmacy.

Materials and methods. An analysis of dissertations, patents, and articles from PubMed, Scopus, and RSCI databases was carried out, with evaluation of the chemical composition and pharmacological activity of the plant.

Results. In the herb of *B. aurei* flavonoids (2.1-2.8 %), saponins (up to 4.5 %), and phenolic compounds (8.0 ± 0.5 % in dry extract) were identified. Plant extracts showed hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant effects. At a dose of 100 mg/kg, the ethanol extract reduced ALT and AST activity in animals by 30-35 %; the flavonoid fraction reduced inflammation by 28 %; and antioxidant activity reached 70-75. Polysaccharide complexes stimulated the immune response [9]. At the same time, potential toxicity risks of certain saikosaponins are noted.

Conclusions. *Bupleurum aurei* Fisch. is a promising source of BAS. Its further study, standardization, and development of extracts may contribute to the creation of domestic herbal medicines, especially with hepatoprotective and immunomodulatory activity.